

Assessment of Abnormal Hemoglobin in Family Members of Patients Diagnosed With Hemoglobinopathies by High Performance Liquid Chromatography

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Abstract:

Introduction: Haemoglobinopathies and thalassemias are among the most common single-gene disorders worldwide, with significant geographical variation in prevalence. High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) has emerged as a sensitive and specific method for identifying hemoglobin variants, offering superior detection capabilities over traditional techniques. This study focuses on utilizing HPLC for familial screening of hemoglobinopathies, aiming to identify and characterize these conditions within families of affected individuals.

Material and Methods: This one-year cross-sectional observational study was conducted in the Department of Biochemistry at a tertiary care hospital in Gujarat. Family members of patients diagnosed with hemoglobinopathies were screened for abnormal hemoglobin variants using HPLC, complemented by peripheral smears, reticulocyte staining, and sickling tests. Blood samples were collected under aseptic conditions, and investigations included CBC analysis and specialized diagnostic tests for hemoglobin variants such as HbS, HbC, and HbF. Flexible arrangements ensured accessibility for family members, with sample collection integrated into hospital workflows or conducted at the 24x7 Central Pathology Lab. Data were statistically analyzed using SPSS, with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$.

Results: In our study, the majority of patients (34.6%) were in the SCT group, followed by BTT and SCD groups (26.9% each). Age distribution showed significant variation ($p = 0.005$), with most patients aged 20–40 years (49.2%) and no cases below 40 years in the STT group. Gender distribution was balanced, with no significant differences ($p = 0.355$). Religion showed significant variation ($p = 0.001$), with Hindus constituting a slight majority (52.3%). SCT had the highest asymptomatic cases (28), while SCD showed unique presentations like crisis and acute chest syndrome. Hemoglobin profiles differed significantly across groups, with BTM showing the highest HbF (86.95) and the Normal group the highest HbAo (84.92). Peripheral smear findings varied, with macrocytic hypochromic blood picture most prevalent in BTT and SCD groups, and dimorphic blood picture rare, observed only in the SCT group.

Conclusion: Our study demonstrated the effectiveness of High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) in diagnosing and differentiating hemoglobinopathies, with significant variations observed in clinical presentations, CBC parameters, hemoglobin variant profiles, and peripheral smear findings across groups.

Keywords: Hemoglobinopathies, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography, Beta-Thalassemia Major, Sickle Cell Disease, Hemoglobin Variants.

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Introduction

Haemoglobinopathies and thalassemias stand out as some of the most prevalent single gene disorders globally. [1] Their occurrence varies significantly depending on geographical location. According to the World Health Organization, approximately 5% of the world's population carries a potentially pathological haemoglobin gene. [2] In India

specifically, the incidence rates of thalassemia trait and sickle cell haemoglobinopathy range between 3-17% and 1-44%, respectively. These figures underscore the significant burden of these genetic disorders and highlight the need for comprehensive screening and management strategies. [3] High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) has

emerged as a highly sensitive and specific technique for the quantification and characterization of hemoglobin variants. [4] This method relies on the separation of hemoglobin molecules based on their individual physicochemical properties, such as size, charge, and affinity for stationary phases. Through precise chromatographic analysis, HPLC enables the identification and quantification of abnormal hemoglobin fractions, including variants associated with hemoglobinopathies. [5]

In the context of familial screening, HPLC offers several advantages over traditional methods such as electrophoresis. Its high resolution and sensitivity allow for the detection of low levels of abnormal hemoglobin, facilitating the identification of carriers and individuals with mild or asymptomatic forms of hemoglobinopathies. In our study, the aim is to identify and characterize hemoglobinopathies within the families of patients diagnosed with these conditions.

Material and Methods

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted in the Department of Biochemistry, a tertiary care hospital in Gujarat. The study was carried out over a period of one year, with the primary goal of evaluating abnormal hemoglobin variants among family members of patients diagnosed with hemoglobinopathies. The study protocol included obtaining detailed medical histories and conducting thorough general examinations. To ensure minimal inconvenience to participants, patient recruitment was integrated into routine hospital workflows, allowing the study to prioritize accessibility and inclusivity for all involved.

For routine investigations, 2 mL of venous blood was collected in K₃EDTA vacutainers under strict aseptic conditions. The samples were processed for complete blood count (CBC) using Mindray BC5300 or BC3600 cell counters. Hemoglobinopathies were screened and characterized using the BIO-RAD D10 High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) system, adhering to the manufacturer's instructions. The HPLC system provided precise detection and identification of hemoglobin variants, including HbS, HbC, HbD, HbE, and HbF. Patients with abnormal hemoglobin levels were requested to invite their family members (parents and siblings) for further screening, which could be conducted either during regular hospital visits or at their convenience in the 24x7 Central Pathology Lab.

To validate the presence of hemoglobinopathies, additional diagnostic tests were performed as needed. Peripheral smears were prepared and stained with Leishman's stain for morphological assessment. Supravital staining with 0.5% new

methylene blue solution was used to identify reticulocytes after incubation at 37°C for 15-20 minutes. Sickling tests were conducted using 2% sodium metabisulphite to detect HbS, with slides sealed and examined microscopically at intervals of 2, 4, and 24 hours. Hemolysate preparation for the modified Betke's method facilitated HbF estimation, while supravital staining for HbH inclusions and heat stability testing for unstable variants were conducted when corresponding HPLC peaks were observed.

Patients diagnosed with hemoglobinopathies were encouraged to bring their immediate family members—parents and siblings—for screening. Flexible arrangements ensured participants could provide samples without disrupting their routine activities. Family members had the option to visit the Central Pathology Lab at any time, as it operated round-the-clock, or to schedule a visit during their regular trips to the hospital. This approach eliminated financial and logistical barriers, allowing comprehensive family screening at no additional cost. The same set of rigorous investigations performed for the primary patients—including CBC, HPLC, peripheral smear analysis, and specialized tests—was applied to the family members' samples.

Data collected during the study were meticulously documented using a standardized proforma and compiled into a master chart. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS software version 21.1. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were used to summarize categorical variables, while continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Comparative analyses were performed using the chi-square test for categorical data and independent t-tests or ANOVA for continuous variables, as appropriate. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

In our study, the distribution of patients across different groups revealed that the majority belonged to the SCT group, comprising 34.6% (45 patients) of the total. This was followed by the BTT and SCD groups, each accounting for 26.9% (35 patients). The Normal and BTM groups had an equal representation of 4.6% (6 patients each), while the STT group had the lowest representation at 2.3% (3 patients).

The age distribution of patients varied significantly across groups ($p = 0.005$). Most patients were in the 20-40 years group (49.2%), followed by 1-20 years (39.2%), with fewer in the 40-60 years (6.2%) and >60 years (5.4%) categories. The SCT group had the widest age range, while BTM and STT were limited to younger age brackets. (Table 1) The sex distribution across groups showed no

significant variation ($p = 0.355$). Females constituted a majority (74 patients, 56.9%) compared to males (56 patients, 43.1%). The SCT and SCD groups had higher female representation, while the STT group consisted entirely of females. Other groups showed a more balanced distribution. The religion distribution across groups showed

significant variation ($p = 0.001$). Hindus constituted a slight majority (68 patients, 52.3%) compared to Muslims (62 patients, 47.7%). The SCT and SCD groups had higher Hindu representation, while the STT group consisted entirely of Muslims. Other groups displayed mixed distributions.

Table 1: Age Distribution of Patients across Groups

Group	1-20 Years	20-40 Years	40-60 Years	>60 Years	Total
Normal	4	2	0	0	6
BTM	4	2	0	0	6
BTT	11	24	0	0	35
SCD	17	16	2	0	35
SCT	12	20	6	7	45
STT	3	0	0	0	3
Total	51	64	8	7	130

The distribution of complaints varied across groups, with notable differences. Fever was most common in the SCT (12 patients) and SCD (10 patients) groups. Weakness was prevalent in BTT (11 patients), SCD (10 patients), and SCT (9 patients). Unique complaints included crisis (4 patients) and acute chest syndrome (1 patient) in

the SCD group, while generalized body pain was observed in BTT (5 patients). SCT had the highest number of patients without complaints (28), followed by BTT (21).

This highlights the diverse clinical presentations associated with different hemoglobinopathy groups.

Table 2: Comparison of CBC Parameters across Groups

Group	HB (Mean \pm SD)	TRBC (Mean \pm SD)	Hct (Mean \pm SD)	MCV (Mean \pm SD)	MCH (Mean \pm SD)	MCHC (Mean \pm SD)	RDW (Mean \pm SD)	Retic Count (Mean \pm SD)
Normal	5.6 \pm 2.8	2.5 \pm 1.3	16.9 \pm 8.2	67.0 \pm 14.8	23.7 \pm 4.0	33.0 \pm 1.2	20.6 \pm 4.3	4.4 \pm 4.9
BTM	6.0 \pm 2.4	2.3 \pm 1.0	18.1 \pm 7.4	65.4 \pm 8.0	22.7 \pm 3.4	29.5 \pm 4.0	24.9 \pm 6.3	3.1 \pm 1.0
BTT	9.7 \pm 2.1	4.3 \pm 1.3	29.6 \pm 6.9	68.1 \pm 11.0	22.9 \pm 5.4	31.3 \pm 2.9	18.7 \pm 4.2	2.3 \pm 1.7
SCD	8.5 \pm 2.7	3.1 \pm 1.1	25.1 \pm 7.7	77.5 \pm 13.3	26.6 \pm 4.8	31.9 \pm 2.8	19.0 \pm 5.1	2.9 \pm 2.2
SCT	9.9 \pm 2.6	3.7 \pm 1.1	29.9 \pm 7.8	80.8 \pm 12.8	27.4 \pm 4.7	33.0 \pm 2.1	17.3 \pm 3.7	2.4 \pm 2.1
STT	7.8 \pm 1.0	3.3 \pm 0.6	24.7 \pm 1.5	72.1 \pm 9.9	25.2 \pm 2.9	32.2 \pm 2.2	21.0 \pm 1.5	2.8 \pm 1.3
P-value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.003	0.006	0.005	0.009

The comparison of hemoglobin values (HbA₀, HbA₂, HbF) across groups revealed significant differences ($p < 0.001$). The BTM group showed the highest HbF levels (86.95), while the Normal group had the highest HbA₀ levels (84.92). The BTT group had elevated HbA₂ levels (4.89),

followed by the STT group (4.63). The SCD group displayed lower HbA₀ levels (17.90) and higher HbF levels (13.76) compared to other groups. These variations reflect the distinct hemoglobin profiles characteristic of different hemoglobinopathies.

Figure 1: Comparison of Hemoglobin Values Across Groups (mean)

The comparison of peripheral smear (PS) comments across groups showed diverse hematological findings. Macrocytic hypochromic blood picture (MHBP) was the most common finding, observed in 65 patients, predominantly in the BTT (26 patients) and SCD (15 patients) groups. Normocytic hypochromic blood picture (NHBP) was noted in 40 patients, with the highest representation in the SCD (16 patients) and SCT (15 patients) groups. Dimorphic blood picture (DBP) was rare, seen only in 3 patients from the SCT group. Other findings, such as normocytic normochromic with MHBP (NN & MHBP), normocytic normochromic blood picture (NNBP), and oval macrocytes, were infrequent, with minimal representation across groups.

Discussion

HPLC has been demonstrated to be a highly sensitive, specific, and reproducible alternative to electrophoresis. Our study classified 130 patients into seven diagnostic groups, with 4.6% normal, 4.6% BTM, 26.9% BTT, 26.9% SCD, 34.6% SCT, 2.3% STT, and 2.3% inconclusive cases, highlighting the diverse distribution of hemoglobin disorders. Comparatively, Khera et al.'s [7] study on HPLC in characterizing hemoglobin profiles among 110 cases revealed that 87 were thalassemic disorders and 23 were hemoglobinopathies. Specifically, 62 cases had β -thalassemia trait, 6 had thalassemia major, 5 had thalassemia intermedia, and 4 had HbH disease. Among hemoglobinopathy cases, HbE trait, HbD Punjab trait, and various compound heterozygotes were noted. Our findings

are consistent with the high prevalence of β -thalassemia and sickle cell disorders in India. [8,9] The carrier frequency for β -thalassemia is 3-4%, with higher frequencies observed in communities such as Sindhis, Punjabis, and Gujaratis. [10] Sickle cell disorders are notably prevalent in tribal populations of Southern, Central, and Western India, reaching up to 48% in some groups. [9] HbE is particularly common in the North Eastern states, with carrier frequencies as high as 50% in certain areas, while HbD is prevalent in about 2% of the population in Punjab. [11]

Globally, over 330,000 affected births are reported annually, primarily due to sickle cell anemia (83%) and thalassemia (17%). [12] Thalassemia carriers are more prevalent worldwide compared to sickle cell carriers, but the higher frequency of the sickle-cell gene in certain regions results in a greater number of affected births. [13] The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that 5.2% of the global population carries significant genomic variants leading to hemoglobinopathies, with 24% being carriers of all known variants. [14]

Our study revealed that the majority of patients with Beta-Thalassemia Trait (BTT) and Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) were within the 20-40 years age range. In contrast, patients with Sickle Cell Trait (SCT) were distributed across all age groups, with a significant number also in the 20-40 years bracket. These findings align with those from other studies. Buch et al. [15] identified a high prevalence of hemoglobinopathies in the 20-30 years age group in Western Maharashtra,

emphasizing the significance of early adulthood in the diagnosis of these disorders. Similarly, Khera et al. [7] observed that most thalassemic disorders were diagnosed in younger individuals.

Our study revealed significant differences in CBC parameters across different diagnostic groups ($p < 0.001$ for most parameters). Notable findings included higher mean corpuscular volume (MCV) and mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH) values in the Sickle Cell Trait (SCT) group compared to others. In β -thalassemia trait cases, increased red cell distribution width (RDW) was observed, consistent with findings by Bhukhanvala et al. [9] indicating a degree of anisopoikilocytosis likely due to concomitant iron deficiency present in 12.9% of our cases. Furthermore, iron deficiency was shown to lower HbA2 concentrations, complicating the diagnosis of β -thalassemia trait (BTT) but still allowing reliable diagnosis based on elevated HbA2 levels, as reported by Madan et al. [16]. A study by Bhukhanvala et al. [9] found that the majority (80%) of samples showed reduced MCV and MCH, similar to findings in our study. However, only 2.1% were confirmed to have BTT upon further testing with cellulose acetate membrane electrophoresis and HPLC, highlighting the challenge of differential diagnosis in populations with high prevalence of iron-deficiency anemia. Mehta and Pandya [17] indicated that individuals with BTT might maintain iron balance better, which could explain variations in RBC indices.

Our study compared hemoglobin variant values (HbAo, HbA2, HbF) across different diagnostic groups, revealing significant differences ($p < 0.001$) in all three parameters. The Beta-Thalassemia Major (BTM) group exhibited a high mean HbF value of 86.95, while the Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) group had a higher mean HbAo value of 17.8971. A study by Bhukhanvala et al. [9] observed that in the context of thalassemia and hemoglobinopathies, HbA2 levels could be reliably used to diagnose β -thalassemia trait (BTT) even in the presence of iron deficiency, as most heterozygotes showed elevated HbA2 (>3.5%). Similarly, Madan et al. [16] reported that iron deficiency did not significantly affect the mean HbA2 levels, which remained elevated in BTT patients. This consistency underscores the reliability of HbA2 as a diagnostic marker despite variations in iron status.

The sample size was relatively small, which may limit the generalizability of our findings. Additionally, the study was confined to a single institution, potentially introducing selection bias. Furthermore, the reliance on HPLC alone, without complementary DNA molecular studies, might have limited the detection of certain hemoglobin variants. Finally, the presence of concomitant iron

deficiency in some patients could have influenced the hematological parameters, complicating the interpretation of results.

Conclusion

Our study on hemoglobinopathies using High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) revealed significant diagnostic insights across various parameters. We observed distinct age and sex distributions, with notable clinical complaints such as fever, weakness, and joint pain associated with specific conditions. Complete Blood Count (CBC) parameters and hemoglobin variant values significantly differed across groups, highlighting the high mean HbF in Beta-Thalassemia Major (BTM) and elevated HbAo in Sickle Cell Disease (SCD). Peripheral Smear (PS) findings also demonstrated characteristic blood picture variations, reinforcing the utility of HPLC in accurately diagnosing and differentiating hemoglobinopathies.

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